

Concerted European action on Sustainable Applications of REFractories

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Deliverable D6.4 - Report about events using “Cerami°K” interactive exhibition

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1 Introduction

As part of Work Package 6 (Dissemination and Proactive Knowledge Transfer to Industry), a mobile scientific exhibition has been developed to emphasize the key role of refractory materials in our daily lives. This initiative, a key outcome of Task 6.4, is titled ‘*Cerami°k - The World of High Temperature Science*’ and is designed to engage the general public, with a particular focus on secondary school students aged 11 to 18. By showcasing ceramic science and refractory research, the exhibition aims to inspire interest in scientific studies and promote careers in the refractory field among young audiences and the wider public. The exhibition has been (and will be) presented and animated by CESAREF Doctoral Candidates (DCs) during open days at participating institutions and public events such as the “European Researchers Night” ensuring broad outreach and impactful engagement.

Initially developed as part of a previous MSCA funded project, ATHOR, the first version (V1) of the CERAMIK exhibition has been reused to engage with the general public while concurrently developing **a new version (V2) of this exhibition which better reflects the objectives of CESAREF**. With this in mind, CESAREF DCs have scrutinised the initial version, V1, and written **new text, chosen new images and conceived new hands-on experiments with a much greater emphasis on sustainability**. Evidently, as both the ATHOR and CESAREF projects are based on refractory materials, any appropriate sections or experiments from the initial version (V1) have been recycled. The second version (V2) of the exhibition is currently in the realisation stage.

Even if the initial intent of this deliverable (D6.4, entitled “Report about events using Cerami°K interactive exhibition”) was to report on the events where the exhibition has been used, we think that, taking into account the **engagement of the DCs in the improvement from V1 to V2**, it is also useful to briefly describe the initial exhibition and the improvements proposed by the DCs. Of course, after these initial sections, the document will also report on the events that have taken place with CERAMI°K (V1) as well as planned future events (using V2 as soon as it is available). It should also be noted that, to reduce travelling costs and maximise the number of events that can be attended (potentially taking place at the same time), some parts of the exhibition will be duplicated.

2 Cerami°K - The World of High Temperature Science

The first version of Cerami°k - V1, with text displayed in both French and English, is organized into four thematic sections, referred to as "islands", each focusing on a distinct topic. Each island features three informational posters complemented by interactive elements such as hands-on experiments, videos and display pieces. A notable highlight of the exhibition is the virtual steel ladle simulation, which allows participants to apply their newly acquired knowledge to test how much steel they can safely produce. A detailed overview of each thematic island is provided in the subsequent sections.

2.1 Island 1 - Ceramics in our society

This “island” highlights the diverse nature of ceramics, detailing their wide range of properties and applications that impact our daily lives. It includes examples of how ceramics are utilized in high-temperature industrial applications, with a particular emphasis on their historical significance and advancements in the steel industry. Figure 1 showcases examples of posters, interactive demonstrations and industrial display pieces featured in the exhibition.

Figure 1 - Posters, hands-on experiments and industrial display pieces presented in Island 1.

The hands-on experiment features images of everyday objects, most of which contain ceramics, alongside one that does not. The audience is challenged to identify the odd-one-out, with additional information about the role of ceramics in each object provided on the reverse side of each picture. The odd-one-out, in this case, has been chosen to challenge the perceptions of the general public. In many cases, the image of glasses will be dismissed due to the glass in the glasses, however, often glasses are actually made with polycarbonate materials.

Display pieces in this section may include ceramic moulds provided by SAFRAN, which are used to grow single metallic crystals into the form required for use as turbine blades in fighter jet engines.

2.2 Island 2 - Industry, ceramics and its challenges

Transitioning from the overview of ceramics in everyday life, this section introduces the audience to the significance and societal impact of the steel industry. It then explores into of various refractory ceramics and the roles used in the lining of steel ladles. Through the hands-on experiment illustrated in Figure 2, participants can explore and physically compare different refractory materials, gaining insight into selecting the appropriate material for specific locations within the steel ladle.

Figure 2 - Posters and hands-on experiments presented in Island 2.

At this stage, the general public is introduced to a ‘virtual steel ladle,’ a larger and more technically complex hands-on experiment than the other experiments in the exhibition. Despite its intricate setup, the interactive and competitive nature of the activity makes it both engaging and educational for participants. It should be noted here that the first version of the software developed for CERAMI^oK - V1 contained some bugs and was not as stable as it could have been. **A great effort was thus carried out at the start of the CESAREF project to resolve these significant issues and this new version of the software is working well.**

In this activity, participants construct the lining of a virtual steel ladle by selecting and placing different refractory bricks in what they believe to be the optimal configuration. Once their design is complete, molten steel is virtually poured into the ladle. The system then simulates and displays the effects of extreme conditions, such as high temperatures and mechanical stresses, on the deterioration of the refractory bricks each time the ladle is filled. The goal is to maximize steel production while staying within safety limits.

The virtual steel ladle is operated using a hands-free interface that combines a projector and a webcam. The webcam detects objects, such as hands or bricks, and processes this information using modified open-source software. This software, integrated with technical data provided by Tata Steel, enables rapid calculations of the effects of various parameters on different areas of the steel ladle. It delivers instant feedback to participants, enhancing the interactive experience. An example of this setup is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - The virtual steel ladle allows the general public to experiment safely.

Each time the steel is poured into the ladle the refractory bricks deteriorate to some extent. In the game this is visually represented by black dots increasingly appearing until the brick is completely shaded out and no longer providing any resistance.

2.3 Island 3 - High temperature ceramics: minerals and sciences

In the third section, visitors will be introduced to the essential properties that refractory bricks must possess to ensure thermo-mechanical and chemical resistance under extreme conditions. The display will cover the key factors considered during the manufacturing process of refractory bricks for industrial applications, alongside the methods and tools employed to analyse their performance and degradation at high temperatures. Complementing the informational posters, interactive demonstrations will include the use of an infrared camera to illustrate the varying thermal behaviours of refractory bricks under heating (Figure 4) and an elastoplasticity experiment to showcase their mechanical properties (Figure 5).

Figure 4 - Posters and Infra-red camera experiment presented in Island 3.

The Elastoplasticity experiment involves the use of a light source, polarising filter and a birefringent material. Applying a force to this material will result in isochromatic lines appearing, these lines indicate how stresses are distributed through the sample (as demonstrated by the hook in Figure 5). The stress concentration in specific parts of the sample is then demonstrated by examining samples with holes drilled in them. These different samples indicate how the presence of different particles (or holes in this case) could affect the cracking behaviour of refractory bricks used in the steel ladle.

Figure 5 - Elastoplasticity experiment a) no force applied to the hook, b) force applied to the hook.

2.4 Island 4 - How scientific research is facing the challenges

A presentation of the advanced research required to optimise the production of metals and enhance the durability of refractory ceramics completes the exhibition. It explores various testing methods and equipment used across different scales to study the behaviour of ceramics, as well as how the results from these tests are integrated into numerical simulations. Additionally, state-of-the-art industrial technologies for real-time monitoring of material degradation are explained, providing insights into their application and benefits.

Interactive experiments accompanying the posters in this section (Figure 6) emphasise the importance of studying materials at varying temperatures. One experiment involves a weight attached to a rubber band fixed to a stand and placed on a scale. As the rubber band is heated, it contracts, slightly lifting the weight. This counter-intuitive outcome engages participants and underscores the critical need to understand material behaviour under different thermal conditions.

Figure 6 - Posters and hands-on experiments presented in Island 4.

3 Augmentation of Cerami°K with a sustainable focus

One of the key advantages of the exhibition is its flexibility. The possibility to pick and choose which islands and experiments to install, depending on the event, available space and the public participating in the event in question, make it particularly interesting for event organisers. With this in mind, **one of the key improvements to the Cerami°K exhibition (V2) is development of an exhibition that can be easily replicated in local languages and stored permanently at the beneficiaries who want to regular use it.**

This flexibility has also enabled the continued used of the exhibition while, **at the same time, developing additional islands. These newly developed islands** reuse many of the hands-on experiments from the original exhibition **introduce topics to the general public that are specific to the CESAREF project** and are described in the following subsections.

3.1 Poster development

All the posters in this exhibition (V2) have been updated to highlight the alignment of the CESAREF project with the European Green Deal, emphasizing its focus on sustainability, innovation and environmental responsibility. The revised posters introduce the political, industrial, and environmental context that has driven the project's collaborations and funding, showcasing the significant role refractories play in our daily lives and their impact on the environment. They also illustrate how research in this field **contributes to achieving Europe's sustainability goals.**

The updated version (V2) will contain an introductory poster, indicating the link between refractory materials and the **European Green Deal**, followed by three updated islands. The first island will introduce materials within the context of the environment. The second island introduces the importance of refractories in our daily lives and the properties that make them particularly interesting. The final island discusses the **challenges we face to achieve Net Zero by 2025** and the approaches that are being investigated in the CESAREF project.

The significant editorial work carried out by the CESAREF DCs and coordinated by Mathilda DERENSY (DC04), João MENEZES CUNHA (DC01) and Glyn DERRICK is now complete. The realisation of these new and updated posters will now be carried out by Centre Sciences.

3.1.1 Updated Island 1 - Materials and the environment, introducing refractories

This island introduces the significant impacts of extraction, processing and disposal of materials such as steel, cement and glass can have on the environment. **The concepts of CO₂ emissions, resource depletion and water pollution are bridged.** The historical and continuing impact refractory materials have had in the advancement of industrial processes is explained and current high-tech applications are presented. AI has been used to produce some of the images that will be included, see Figure 7.

Figure 7 - AI generated image to encourage the audience to consider how much steel, glass and cement they consume.

3.1.2 Updated Island 2 - Importance and properties of refractories

The current industrial **challenges faced by energy intensive industries** and how cutting-edge research, state-of-the-art-technology and up-coming methodologies can be used to address the potential solutions is discussed here. More detailed explanations of how the structure effects the mechanical and physical properties of refractories is given alongside details regarding the **use of large-scale experiments, such as synchrotron facilities**, to analyse different materials. To complement the real-world experimental methods, numerical modelling techniques are discussed to complete this island.

3.1.3 New Island 3 - Energy, Digitalisation, Hydrogen and Recycling

A **completely new island** has also been introduced to present cutting-edge research activities, including advancements in **machine learning, digitalization, the use of hydrogen as a sustainable fuel source and the recycling of refractory materials**. The posters further discuss how **life cycle assessment (LCA)** can be applied to evaluate and minimize environmental impacts in this sector.

These updates reflect CESAREF's objective of supporting Europe's energy intensive industries transition towards a circular economy and climate neutrality.

3.2 Hands-on experiment development

Several **new hands-on experiments** are also under development. For example, to explain **what happens at a molecular level to the microstructure of a material when it is heated**, a flat, transparent Perspex/Plexiglass box will be filled with ball bearings (atoms), see Figure 8. When agitated by the public the ball bearings will settle, leaving occasional deformations. When materials are heated, at a molecular level, an increase in vibrations is observed. For this experiment the box will be vibrated (to represent heating) and the public can see the effect, on the microstructure of a material, when heat is applied.

Figure 8 - a) Perspex box with ball bearings, b) before vibrating and c) after vibrating.

Another example of an experiment under development is the **ceramic xylophone** (Figure 9). At the simplest level, this hands-on experiment demonstrates that different materials have different properties. However, the science behind this simple experiment is more complicated, involving the calculations of frequency and Young's modulus. **These principles are applied in cutting edge technologies such as Resonance Frequency and Damping Analyzer (RFDA).**

Figure 9 - The ceramic xylophone.

To conclude this Section 3 - Augmentation of Cerami°K with a sustainable focus, it should be noted that a huge effort has been made by several **CESAREF DCs** during the first part of the **CESAREF project** to conceptualise the required improvements to align with the sustainable aspects of the project. This conceptual work is now to be realised by Centre Sciences and as such, there are currently very limited images available of Cerami°K exhibition - V2 to be shown in this deliverable.

4 CERAMIK in use

The general public have had the opportunity to interact with the Cerami°K exhibition (currently in its version 1) on multiple occasions since the start of the CESAREF project. The events that have been attended and those that are planned are listed in the following subsections.

4.1 Attended events

The events that have already been attended by the Cerami°K exhibition are listed in Table 1 and described in the following subsections.

Table 1 - Events attended by the Cerami°K exhibition between October 2022 and September 2024.

Event	Dates	Location	Information	Participants
Official inauguration of the CERAMIK exhibition	18/01/2023 - 15/02/2023	University of Orleans	A month-long event	General public
CESAREF Kick-off in Brussels	20/02/2023-24/02/2023	Brussels	A 5-day consortium event	30 Participants - CESAREF consortium
Fête de la Science	12/10/2023 - 14/10/2023	Limoges	A 3-day event	100+ participants - general public
University of Limoges Open day	03/02/2024	Limoges	Open day	60+ participants - general public
Commission Mixte GFC SF2M Matériaux Céramiques Réfractaires - Limoges	07/02/2024 - 08/02/2024	Limoges	A 2-day event in	50+ participants from the refractories industry
Journée de la physique	04/04/2024	Limoges	A report from France 3 can be seen here .	24 Schools and colleges from Limoges were involved - 250 students in total
European researchers' night	27/09/2024	Limoges	The local television company 7ALimoges covered the event, the report can be seen here .	1443 participants - general public

4.1.1 Official inauguration of the CERAMIK exhibition

The CERAMI°K exhibition was officially inaugurated at the University of Orléans on January 23rd 2023. Organized by the LaMé laboratory and hosted at the Polytech - Vinci site, the exhibition provided a unique platform for scientific exploration and public engagement.

Prior to its official inauguration, the exhibition was opened to the general public starting January 18, 2023, allowing visitors to explore its engaging displays and interactive features. It remained accessible until February 15, 2023, offering nearly a month of opportunities for attendees to learn about the innovative applications of ceramics in various fields. Some photos of the event are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Photos from the official inauguration of the CERAMIK exhibition at the University of Orleans (18/01/2023 - 15/02/2023).

4.1.2 CESAREF Kick-off in Brussels

The CESAREF Kick-off event, held in Brussels from February 20 to February 27, 2023, marked the official launch of this ambitious European doctoral network focused on sustainable applications of refractory materials. The event brought together a diverse group of participants, including doctoral candidates (DCs), academic researchers and industrial partners from across Europe. This gathering set the foundation for the network’s innovative research and training initiatives as well as its communication activities.

Throughout the week-long event, attendees engaged in numerous presentations and specialized training workshops designed to equip the doctoral candidates with essential scientific, technical, and transferable skills relevant to the project’s goals. Throughout the event the CERAMI^oK exhibition was installed to generate maximum discussion on how best to communicate about refractory materials. **Brainstorming sessions were organized to refine and optimize the exhibition, ensuring it effectively communicated the project’s focus on sustainability, energy efficiency and the life cycle management of refractory materials.** Some photos of the event are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 - Photos from the CESAREF Kick-off event in Brussels (20/02/2023-24/02/2023).

4.1.3 Fête de la Science

The Fete de la Science is an annual French national event, free and open to all, that took place nationwide from the 12-14th October 2023. At the initiative of the Ministry of Higher Education and Research and Innovation, and supported by the Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region, the Fete de la Science encourages the engagement with the general public enthusiastic about science. Professionals, researchers, technicians, engineers, laboratory workers and even amateurs from all disciplines meet the public in order to better promote research, its discoveries and its professions.

The CeramiK Exhibition was presented at the Centre Européen de la Céramique, Limoges, France and a stand by the [IRCER](#) laboratory was installed at the [ESTER](#) Technopole, Limoges. CESAREF DCs were on hand to present different aspects of the exhibition and local translators, as well as the project coordinator Marc HUGER, were on hand to help with any language issues. Some photos of the event are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Photos from the Fête de la Science event in Limoges (12/10/2023 - 14/10/2023).

4.1.4 University of Limoges Open day

On Saturday 3rd February 2024 the **University of Limoges held its annual open day**. This was an excellent opportunity for students and parents to clarify the orientation of future studies, meet teaching staff and discover the university. The CERAMI°K exhibition provided an excellent back-drop to this event, showing an often-hidden side of ceramics and some of the potential career paths that are associate. Some photos of the event are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 - Photos from the University of Limoges Open day (03/02/2024).

4.1.5 Commission Mixte GFC SF2M Matériaux Céramiques Réfractaires - Limoges

The Joint Commission of the **Groupe Français de la Céramique** and the **Société Française de Métallurgie et de Matériaux (GFC/SF2M)** organized 2 days of innovative insights on "Refractory Ceramic Materials" at IRCER Limoges from 7th-8th February 2024. Five CESAREF PhDs were involved in the event, where the CERAMI°K exhibition was on display. A photo of the event is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 - GFC/SF2M 2 days of innovative insights on "Refractory Ceramic Materials" (07/02/2024 - 08/02/2024).

4.1.6 Journée de la physique

The **Journée de la Physique 2024 at the University of Limoges** was held on April 4, 2024, as part of national efforts to promote physics education and research. Organized in collaboration with the CNRS and academic institutions, the event aimed to engage students and the public through interactive demonstrations, workshops, and lectures. Some photos of the event are shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15 - Photos from the Journée de la physique (04/04/2024).

4.1.7 European researchers' night

The **European Researchers' Night 2024 in Limoges**, was part of a Europe-wide scientific outreach initiative, which occurred on September 27, 2024, at the BFM (Bibliothèque Francophone Multimédia) from 6:30 PM to midnight. Organized by the University of Limoges under the national theme "Hors Piste" (Off the Beaten Path), the event emphasizes unconventional research approaches, interdisciplinary collaboration and public engagement. Some photos of the event are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 - Photos from the European Researchers' Night 2024 in Limoges (27/09/2024).

The general public, from primary school children to pensioners from all backgrounds, was enthusiastic to engage with the exhibition. Often posing challenging questions to our researchers and testing the hands-on experiments in ways we were not expecting. For example, the infrared camera proved popular to see the difference when people were wearing glasses or not, see Figure 17.

Figure 17 - The general public engaging with the interactive activities.

4.2 Planned events

Events that the CESAREF are currently planning to attend are described in the table below. This is not a definitive list of events and further events will most likely be attended.

Table 2 - Events planned for the Cerami°K exhibition to attend between October 2024 to September 2026.

Event	Dates	Location	Information	Participants
European researchers' night	September 2025	Limoges, University of Limoges Liege, University of Liege	1 evening	300+ participants - general public
Science Night	November 2025	Aachen, RWTH	1 day	50+ participants - general public
Open days	December 2025	Aachen, RWTH	1 day, RWTH	50+ participants - general public
Vienna Research Festival	March 2026	Vienna, TUW	A 3-day event	300+ participants - general public
Printemps des Sciences	March 2026	Liege, University of Liege	1 week	500+ participants - general public
Espace Muséal Andenne	2026	Liege, University of Liege	https://lephare-andenne.be/ema/	300+ participants - general public

5 Conclusion

Cerami°K - The World of High Temperature Science transforms cutting-edge research from an often-overlooked industrial sector into an engaging, multidisciplinary experience for diverse audiences. Designed to communicate complex scientific concepts, the exhibition employs audio, visual and hands-on learning tools to spark curiosity and inspire future generations of researchers.

The exhibition uses clear, non-technical language paired with carefully curated visuals that balance aesthetic appeal with educational clarity, ensuring ideas resonate with viewers of all backgrounds. Interactive experiments, such as comparing material weights and textures, complement informational posters, while counterintuitive demonstrations challenge assumptions and encourage critical thinking. A multisensory approach, including kinetic elements like a virtual steel ladle simulation, bridges theoretical concepts with real-world industrial applications, fostering deeper understanding through direct interaction.

By presenting fundamental research on refractory ceramics in a playful, approachable format, Cerami°K highlights their vital role in steel production, aerospace and everyday technologies.